

Several possible analytical solutions for electrostatic fields

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Abstract: If the analytical solutions for these possible electrostatic fields are correct, then we can directly obtain the relationship between the basic physical constants.

Key words: universal Gravitational constant, electrostatic field, basic atomic mass, proton radius.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1. \frac{(e_0)^2}{(4\pi)(\epsilon_0)(a_0)^2} = \frac{(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2}{(a_0)} \\ 2. \left[\frac{(e_0)}{(4\pi)(\epsilon_0)} \right]^2 / (e_0) = \frac{1}{2} (m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2 / (e_0) = \frac{(m_{\text{atom}})(c)^2}{(2\pi)(R_\infty)} / (e_0) = 13.6 \\ 3. \left[\frac{(e_0)}{(4\pi)(\epsilon_0)(a_0)} \right]^2 = \left[\frac{(m_{\text{atom}})(G_N)}{(4\pi)(a_0)^2(2\pi)^2(a_0)^2} \right]^2 = \frac{(m_{\text{atom}})}{(2\pi)^4(r_a)(r_e)(R_\infty)(a_0)} = \frac{(m_e)(m_{\text{atom}})(R_\infty)}{(4\pi)(a_0)^2(2\pi)^2(a_0)^2(2\pi)(r_a)} \end{array} \right.$$

Reference: none.